

Fertilizer management — inorganic sources

Effect of Zn on grain yield and Zn uptake by lowland rice in South Gujarat

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One-fourth of South Gujarat rice soils have Zn deficiency (less than 0.60 mg kg⁻¹ DTPA-extractable Zn). Another 39%, classified as medium-deficient (0.6-1.0 mg kg⁻¹ DTPA-extractable Zn), will probably worsen from continuous waterlogging of ricefields. Presently, a blanket application of 2 kg Zn ha⁻¹ is recommended but considered insufficient for low Zn soils.

We examined the effect of 0, 5.6, 11.2, and 16.8 kg Zn ha⁻¹ on Jaya (coarse grain variety) and GR.11 (fine grain variety) in field experiments during 1992 and 1993 monsoon seasons. The experiments were conducted in a randomized block design with four replications in plots of 6.0- × 3.0- m on Vertic Ustochrept soils. Chemical analysis showed that the soil was low in DTPA-extractable Zn (0.60 mg kg⁻¹) and alkaline KMnO₄-extractable N (230 kg ha⁻¹), medium in Olsen P (12.4 kg ha⁻¹) and high in neutral N NH₄O Ac-extractable K (283 kg ha⁻¹) with a pH of 7.9 without problems of salinity or sodicity. Nitrogen was applied at 100 kg ha⁻¹ and P at 22 kg ha⁻¹. The entire amount of Zn (as ZnSO₄·7H₂O), P, and 40 kg N were applied before puddling. The remaining N was applied in two equal splits each after 20 and 45 d of transplanting. The sources of N and P were diammonium phosphate (DAP) and urea. The crop was irrigated during drought periods. At harvest, diacid extracts of grain and straw samples were analyzed for Zn using an AA spectrophotometer.

Pooled analysis on grain yield and total Zn uptake data indicated nonsignificant first- and second-order inter-

2. Relationship between Zn level and total Zn uptake.

actions between Zn levels, years, and varieties. In main effects, only the Zn levels were significant for yield and uptake. A quadratic relationship was found between Zn levels and pooled yield and pooled total Zn uptake (Figs. 1 and 2). Solving the equation

$$X_{(opt)} = \frac{-b}{2c}$$

where $X_{(opt)}$ = optimum Zn dose for uptake, indicated a continuation of Zn uptake up to 14.3 kg Zn ha⁻¹ and a yield increase up to 13.6 kg Zn ha⁻¹. Solving the equation,

$$X_{(e)} = \frac{1}{2c} \left(-\frac{q}{p} - b \right)$$

where $X_{(e)}$ = dose of Zn for economic yield, q = cost of Zn at Rs 54.76 kg⁻¹, p = price of rice at Rs 4500 t⁻¹, indicated an economic dose of 11.9 kg Zn ha⁻¹. Thus the present recommendation of 2 kg Zn ha⁻¹ is inadequate for rice production in Zn-deficient lowland soils of South Gujarat. Our results using these two rice varieties indicate the need to increase Zn application to about 12 kg ha⁻¹ for these soils. ■

Optimization of potassium application in acid soils of Tamil Nadu

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To assess the response of K in Typic Ustropepts soils (pH 5.6; EC 0.24 dS m⁻¹) and to optimize its application for low-land irrigated rice (37.3 kg available K ha⁻¹), we laid out a trial of variety ASD18 on 3.4- × 4.5-m plots with 15- × 10-cm hill spacing during the 1995 dry season (June-September) with six levels of K₂O and two levels of lime (as CaO) using a factorial randomized

Table 1. Influence of K on grain yield of rice in acid soils.

K ₂ O (kg ha ⁻¹)	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)		
	L0 ^a	L1	Mean
0	4.6	5.1	4.8
25	4.7	5.2	5.0
50	4.9	5.5	5.2
75	5.1	6.5	5.8
100	5.3	6.1	5.7
125	5.5	6.0	5.8
CD (p=0.05)			
Potash	0.09		
Lime	0.11		
Potash × lime	0.28		

^aL0 = zero lime, L1 = lime at 2.8 t ha⁻¹.

block design with three replications (Table 1). Potash was applied per treatment in two equal splits as basal and 30 d after transplanting (DT) (panicle initiation stage); K₂O as basal at 50 kg ha⁻¹; and N at 125 kg ha⁻¹ with 50 kg ha⁻¹ as basal and 25 kg ha⁻¹ on 15, 30, and 45 DT. Grain yield was assessed by plot, and yield component traits were recorded on five plants in a single replication.

Significant differences were found between the levels of K, lime, and their interaction. At all K levels, lime application increased grain yield. Application at 75 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ with lime resulted in the highest grain yield of 6.5 t ha⁻¹.

Without lime application, K response was low and at 125 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ the grain yield was only 5.5 t ha⁻¹ (Table 1). Increases were also observed in plant height, productive tillers, panicle length, filled grains panicle⁻¹, and 1000-grain weight (Table 2).

Potassium is an excellent replacer of Al in exchangeable clay complexes. Soluble Al (hindrance to P uptake) is precipitated into aluminum hydroxide by the application of lime, which mitigates the toxic effect of Al and increases the uptake of K in acid soils. In these acid soils, 75 kg K₂O ha⁻¹ applied with 2.8 t lime ha⁻¹ were optimum for rice cultivation. ■

Table 2. Effect of K and lime application on plant characters of rice grown on acid soil.^a

K ₂ O (kg ha ⁻¹)	Plant height (cm)		Productive tillers hill ⁻¹ (no.)		Panicle length (cm)		Filled grains panicle ⁻¹ (no.)		1000-grain weight(g)	
	L0 ^b	L1 ^b	L0	L1	L0	L1	L0	L1	L0	L1
	0	80	82	6.1	6.3	18	20	57	64	21.0
25	80	83	6.2*	6.5	20	21	80	81	21.0	21.5
50	81	83	5.9	6.8	20	21	84	87	21.6	22.0
75	82*	88*	6.2*	6.8	21*	22*	89	97*	21.8	22.1
100	81	89*	6.2*	6.9*	21*	22*	93*	106*	22.0*	22.1
125	83*	92*	6.2*	6.9*	21*	22*	104*	106*	22.0	22.6*

^a * = significant at the 5% level. ^b L0 = zero lime, L1 = lime at 2.8 t ha⁻¹

Increased yield of lowland rice with late N application in the reproductive phase and at high N rates

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Nitrogen deficiency results from current recommendations of local best-split N applications. A field experiment was designed to test the hypothesis that supplying a large proportion of N during the reproductive phase (1 wk before panicle initiation, at booting, and at heading) would eliminate this deficiency and improve yields. Applications at recommended N (120 kg ha⁻¹) and at an increased level (180 kg N ha⁻¹)

were carried out in a split-plot design (N rates in main plots and N splits in subplots). The experiments used four replications during the wet seasons of 1988, 1989, 1991, and 1992 at Pantnagar (29° N, 79° E, and 244 m) on silt loam with pH 7.9, 1.1% organic C, CEC 20 meq 100 g⁻¹ soil, 0.1% total N, 13.9 kg available P (Olsen) ha⁻¹, and 202 kg available K ha⁻¹ (NH₄OAc extraction). Rice variety Pant Dhan 4 (134 d duration) was sown 1 Jun in a nursery and transplanted between 5 and 15 Jul in the 4 yr with basal applications of 18 kg P ha⁻¹, 33 kg K ha⁻¹, and 10 kg Zn ha⁻¹.

Time of N application had a significant effect in all years except 1989 (Table 1). In general, the results suggest that controlling the supply of N during initial growth stages and following

Table 1. Effect of N applications on grain yield of rice.

Treatment	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)				Mean
	1988	1989	1991	1992	
<i>N rate (kg ha⁻¹)</i>					
120	6.7	7.0	5.2	7.4	6.6
180	7.2	7.7	6.7	7.7	7.3
LSD (0.05)	0.4	0.7	0.7	0.3	
<i>Time of N application^a</i>					
T1	6.5	7.2	6.0	7.3	6.8
T2	6.7	7.3	—	—	7.0
T3	17.4	7.4	6.2	7.8	7.2
T4	7.2	7.4	5.8	8.0	7.1
T5	7.2	7.4	—	—	7.3
T6	6.7	7.4	—	—	7.1
T7	—	7.5	5.8	7.4	6.9
LSD (0.05)	0.5	ns	0.4	0.5	
Interaction	ns	ns	ns	ns	
CV (%)	6	7	5	5	

^a T1 = 1/2 basal, 1/4 at tillering, 1/4 at 6-7 d before panicle initiation (DBPI); T2 = 2/3 basal, 1/3 at 6-7 DBPI; T3 = 1/5 basal, 1/5 at tillering, 1/5 at 6-7 DBPI, 1/5 at booting, 1/5 at heading; T4 = 1/5 basal, 1/5 at tillering, 1/5 at 6-7 DBPI, 1/5 at booting, 1/5 (foliar spray) at heading; T5 = 1/4 basal, 1/4 at tillering, 1/6 at 6-7 DBPI, 1/6 at booting, 1/6 at heading; T6 = 1/4 basal, 1/4 at tillering, 1/6 at 6-7 DBPI, 1/6 at booting, 1/6 (foliar spray) at heading; T7 = 1/2 basal, 1/8 at tillering, 1/8 at 6-7 DBPI, 1/8 at booting, 1/8 at heading.

Table 2. Economics of late N application at booting and heading stages over recommended N split application at two N rates.^a

Economic factor	N rates (kg ha ⁻¹)	
	120	180
1. Added labor for topdressing of urea per ha required at booting and heading	1	1
2. Wage of labor (US\$ d ⁻¹)	1.2	1.2
3. Added labor cost (US\$)	1.2	1.2
4. Added yield of rice obtained from late application (t ha ⁻¹)	0.5	0.4
5. Price of rice (US\$ t ⁻¹)	100	100
6. Added return (US\$)	50	40
7. Added net return from late application (item 6-item 3)	48.8	38.8

^aCost of cultivation was the same for both treatments except for the extra cost incurred in topdressing of urea at booting and heading. Av of 1988, 1989, 1991, and 1992 data.

with applications of larger amounts of N topdressing in the reproductive stages bring higher yields than the recommended N split application.